

Benthic survey protocol to determine coral cover, abundance, and growth form diversity

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Summary

Corals and the reefs they built are being decimated by anthropogenic impact, hastening the need to develop strategies that can mitigate the effects of local stressors and global climate change [1–3]. To this end, short-term acute heat stress assays provide a standardized thermal stress diagnostic to identify colonies, populations, and species with superior thermotolerance at scale, e.g. for restoration purposes or to study their genetic/genomic underpinnings [4–11]. Such data is greatly enhanced through the collection of environmental data to contextualize measured thermal tolerance differences [12,13], as thermal resilience is likely a product of genetic and environmental differences [5,6,14]. Thus, when assessing thermal tolerance of coral colonies, it is vital to assess the status of the coral reef as a whole. Important parameters for instance are live coral cover or species richness (biodiversity) [15]. These parameters can be collected during a benthic survey, and there are many different methods for conducting benthic surveys, with some widely used methods being line intercept transects (LITs) [16], point intercept transects (PITs) [16], and photoquadrats [17]. Here we present a standardized photoquadrat protocol with subsequent analysis using CoralNet to contextualize measured thermotolerance differences with overall reef condition [18]. Photoquadrats have the advantage that data can be collected in the form of an underwater image while being analyzed later, allowing for flexibility and time-saving in the field. Further, it provides the possibility to work with divers with limited taxonomic experience/expertise. Importantly, desk-based digital analysis allows for standardized exploration with the ability to upload raw and processed data into databases for cross-study comparison.

Overall objective

Coral reef benthic survey protocol and subsequent analysis using coralnet to contextualize short-term thermal stress assay (CBASS) data

Employed method

Line transect with photoquadrats and subsequent analysis of random points with <https://coralnet.ucsd.edu> [18]

Step-by-step protocol

I. Transects/Data collection

Lay out a 50m line transect at sample collection depth using transect tape (e.g., [link](#)), parallel to the reef crest.

NOTE: Scout the reef site and select a representative section of the reef for the transect.

NOTE: Stretch the transect line tightly and close to the bottom if possible.

TIP: Place zip-tied weight at the end of the transect tape to immobilize it.

- Move along the transect line (backwards: from end of tape/spool to 0m, so you don't have to swim the same distance twice)
- Place the 50 x 50 cm quadrat at every 5 m intercept next to the transect tape (starting at 50 m). Line up the quadrat so you can read the meter marking on the transect tape Fig. 1).
- Record depth of transect.

Figure 1. Scheme of quadrat placement.

NOTE: We use PVC piping to make quadrats. Drill holes in the PVC piping to facilitate the escape of air when entering the water, so the is not positively buoyant.

- Take a photo of each quadrat, while making sure the photo is:
 - unobstructed & in focus
 - approximately the same distance for each photo.
 - taken from directly above the photoquadrat, so that the photoquadrat still has the shape of a square in the photo.
- Repeat the entire procedure above for a second transect.

NOTE: Taking multiple photos per quadrat is advisable and helps mitigate difficult environmental conditions.

NOTE: A minimum of two transects should be performed. More than two transects can help with extremely variable reef sites. But there are significant diminishing returns when increasing the number of replicates.

II. Data analysis

Data preparation

Preprocessing of images

- If more than one photo per quadrat was taken, select the best one based on the parameter listed in the “Data collection” section.
- All images should be named in a consistent manner prior to analysis. The image name should include the date the transect was taken (YYYYMMDD), the location at which the transect was taken (country and region), the transect number, and the location of the image along the transect (e.g. 0m, 5m, etc.).

NOTE: It is advisable to crop and pre-align all images in order to standardize the quadrat position between all photos. This enables faster annotation by defining a standard annotation area for all images allowing to avoid the manual annotation area selection for each photo in “Step 3. Image Annotation settings” below.

CoralNet as a benthic image analysis tool

CoralNet (<https://coralnet.ucsd.edu/>) is one of multiple websites that can be used for benthic image analysis. It is free, open source and allows for collaboration on benthic analysis projects. Moreover, CoralNet presents a clear and intuitive design, making it easy to use for anyone regardless of their background. Apart from manual annotation of images it offers semi and fully automated annotations using a machine learning tool, expediting the benthic image analysis over time.

Creating a CoralNet account

All analysts (beside the source admin) need to create a CoralNet account before being able to use the website and upload any images. An account can be created on the CoralNet website. For this, visit the CoralNet website (<https://coralnet.ucsd.edu/>), select “Register”, and enter the required information.

Adding other analysts

To add other analysts to the source an admin user has to do the following:

From the source homepage select “Admin” on the navigation bar.

1. Add the CoralNet username of analysts to the recipient field of the send invite section.
2. Select level of access permission to source:
 - View - Can only view.
 - Edit – Can edit the metadata, annotate and upload images to the source.
 - Admin – Can change the labelset, change the source information and invite other people to the source.

Creating a source

NOTE: On CoralNet project datasets are referred to as sources.

NOTE: Since each source has an independent automated annotator. We recommend a new source should be created for each region, or more generally, for sets of transects where you expect a similar taxonomic diversity. This enables more accurate predictions, without compromising the effectiveness due to variability of conditions between sites.

NOTE: CoralNet allows to reuse a trained annotator with different sources. We do not recommend reusing a trained classifier if the image quality varies significantly.

- To create a new source go to the home interface of CoralNet. In the top left corner select "Create a new Source".

Figure 2. CoralNet home page "new Source" button.

- You subsequently need to supply the following:
 1. General info:
 - a) **Source Name:** Name of the project/region
 - b) **Visibility:** public or private
 - c) **Affiliation:** University or research team
 - d) **Description:** Summary of the project
 2. Metadata to include in source:
 - a) Standard metadata fields are provided (i.e.: date, camera, latitude, longitude, etc.)
 - b) Auxiliary fields should be added and must include:
 1. County
 2. Reef site
 3. Transect number
 4. Transect meter (e.g. 0m, 5m, etc.)
 3. Image annotation settings
 - a) Annotation area: If images have been pre-cropped define a standard image annotation area that matches the internal area of the quadrat. If not, leave to the default (X: 0 - 100% / Y: 0 - 100%). Setting the full image as the annotation area. Annotation area should then be redefined manually for each photo.
 - b) Point generation method: Set to "simple random" with at least 20 annotation points.

NOTE: Generally, 20 annotation points using the simple random point generation method are sufficient to give a solid representation of the coral cover at each site. But other algorithms to generate annotation points are available.

4. World location
 - a) Average Latitude and Longitude of your dataset. This will allow your Source to be displayed on the CoralNet map.

NOTE: Sources are displayed automatically in the CoralNet map if they contain at least 100 images and no "test" title.

5. Finalize with the button "Create source".

Uploading the images and metadata to CoralNet

To upload your images to CoralNet:

1. Select "Upload" from the source homepage navigation bar.
2. Select "Upload images"
3. Select all the images you want to upload to the specific source.

NOTE: In addition to uploading the images, you can upload a CSV metadata file. Each image should have one row, and each metadata field should have one column. A more detailed description of the format required can be found in the upload metadata section by selecting the small yellow question mark.

NOTE: The metadata can be edited at any later time point by anyone with editing or admin permissions. To do so, select the source you want to edit, then select "Metadata" from the source homepage navigation bar. You can then enter the metadata either for each image individually or multiple images simultaneously by selecting the checkbox of the images to the very left. Once the editing is completed, select "Save Edits".

Creating a labelset

Before starting the annotation process, a labelset needs to be created. Creating a fixed labelset for a source ensures that consistent labeling can be used across all associated images.

When creating the labelset, all labels should be on the same classification level, e.g. different growth forms, as points can only be assigned a single label. In our labelset, we selected different hard coral growth forms (branching, columnar, encrusting, foliose, free-living, massive) each healthy and bleached (e.g., branching healthy, branching bleached), soft coral, other invertebrate, dead, and diseased corals, hard substrate, algae, CCA, and unknown. This provides a broad insight into the percentage coral cover of healthy, bleached, and dead corals and their different growth forms at each site, without requiring the annotation to a certain taxonomy. However, some common genera that are easy to annotate may be useful and can be included without raising the training required for the annotator, e.g. *Acrpora*, *Pocillopora*, *Porites*, etc. An "unknown" or similar label should always be included in the labelset for unidentifiable areas within the images.

Our labelset can be uploaded as a CSV file by selecting "Import a labelset from a CSV file" and is available as part of this release.

To manually create a labelset:

1. Select "Labelset" in the Source homepage navigation bar.
2. Select "Choose labels for your labelset"
3. Use the search function to find pre-made labels or create your own.
 - a. To create a new label, select "Create a new label" You will then need to enter the name, short code, functional group, description, and an example image.
 - b. When creating new labels, the names and short codes should be consistent with the already existing labels of the label set.
4. Once all the labels have been selected, select "Create labelset" at the bottom of the table. You will then be redirected to a table containing your Source's labelset.

NOTE: You can edit the labelset at any time by selecting "Add/Remove labels". Select or deselect the appropriate labels and "Save Changes" when done. Editing labelsets will require complete re-annotation of all points in the image and for the sake of consistency, all images of a source should use the same labelset. Thus, it is sensible to spend some time with 'test annotating' images to get a feel what labels are good to have, and only after that start annotating the actual transects.

NOTE: A list of "All Labels" can be seen in the form of a table that includes label name, functional group, popularity, status, and default short code.

CoralNet Annotation Settings

NOTE: These settings need to be applied once before starting the image analysis process.

1. Select "Images" from the source homepage navigation bar, then select the first image you want to annotate.
2. Select "Annotation Tool" at the top right corner to access the annotation tool window.
3. In the Annotation Tool window, select "Settings".
4. In the resulting pop-up you can customize the following: Point marker type, Point marker size, Point number size, Point colors (4 categories)
5. Ensure "Point marker is scaled" and "Show machine annotations" is checked.
6. Save these settings

Image analysis

1. From the image section of the source page select the image. This opens the "Image Details" page.
2. If the images have not been pre-cropped and aligned to the annotation area, you need to set the annotation area:
 - a. In the "Annotation and point location status" section, select "Edit" beside "Annotation area".

Figure 3. Annotation and point location status section from the CoralNet image page.

- b. Manipulate the yellow rectangle so that it matches up with the boundaries of the quadrat frame. Try to line up the rectangle to ensure as much as the area within the quadrat is available for annotation, while excluding areas outside the quadrat from the selection (See *image below*).

Figure 4. Example of selection of annotation area.

- c. Save the changes.

NOTE: changing the annotation area will regenerate the points. So it must be done before proceeding further with the annotation. Otherwise, all the point information will be lost during the regeneration process.

3. Select "Annotation Tool". This will take you to the page where you will analyze each image.
4. Select the first cell in the ID column on the far-right side of the screen (analysis point #1)
5. This point will change to the color designated for the selected data point (the default setting is green).

Figure 5. Example "Annotation Tool" interface

6. Identify the object beneath the point using the relevant benthic category label from the bottom of the thread. Use the zoom feature as required to get all the necessary details.

NOTE: It is important to note that the label should be assigned to the upper visible layer only, e.g. a rock covered in turf algae should be annotated as "turf algae", not "rock".

7. After selecting the correct label, you will be automatically advanced to the next point.
8. Repeat these annotation steps until all points on the image are classified.

NOTE: If there is an image that has large sections of the same label type, (e.g., large patches of sand with multiple points), you can also use the "Rectangle Select" function in the annotation tool bar on the right-hand side of the page.

9. Save your progress by clicking "Save Progress".
10. When all points have been classified and saved, "ALL DONE" will appear at the bottom of the column.
11. You can then move on to the next image to be analyzed.
12. Repeat analysis steps for each image until all allocated images have been analyzed.

Automated annotator settings

This CoralNet feature helps expedite the analysis process by providing automated annotations based on machine learning. Once 20 images per source have been fully annotated, the CoralNet automated annotator will start to suggest annotations. The automatic suggestions, as well as the relative confidence of each suggestion will then be displayed while annotating the point.

Figure 6. Example automated annotator suggestion

NOTE: You can set the confidence threshold for the automated annotator suggestion on the “Edit Source” page. All suggested annotations with confidence over the threshold will be confirmed automatically.

NOTE: Initially, the threshold should be set to 100% while the robot is being trained for your Source. This can then be adjusted as its training progresses. Annotation confidence level can be seen from the source homepage and details can be found in the “backend” section of the source page.

Exporting the data

To export the annotated data:

1. Select the "Images" tab in the Source navigation bar.
2. Select all the images whose data you would like to export using the dropdown menus in the "Browse Images" box.
3. At the bottom of the page, in the "Image Actions" box, select:
 - a. “Export Image Covers” to create a .csv or an .xlsx file with percentage cover data (default filename = percent_covers.xlsx)
 - b. "Export Annotations, CSV" to create a “annotations.csv” file.
 - i. The default includes columns for: image name, pixel row (Y), pixel column (X) and Label.
 - ii. The optional columns include:
 - Annotator information (i.e.: username of analyst, “Imported” or “robot”)
 - Machine suggestions (the machine’s top 5 suggestions)
 - Image metadata- auxiliary (i.e.: the user provided metadata)
 - image metadata - other (i.e.: the main metadata - default to CoralNet)

NOTE: the annotations.csv file does not include a column for point number. However, the entries are ordered by point number in the spreadsheet. You can create a point number column before manipulating the spreadsheet.

NOTE: You can also export metadata separately; although, this data can be included in the annotation.csv file

NOTE: The export download takes place at a rate of 1 min per 5000 annotations. If the dataset to be downloaded is large, consider filtering the search to a smaller number of images before exporting.

4. Use the exported percent_covers.csv and annotation.csv file in downstream data analysis.

III. Data integration

CoralNet does not provide statistical analysis so this must be done separately.

Annotation data from CoralNet can be exported as a CSV file and in CPCe compatible format. This simplifies data integration and further downstream data analysis.

Calcification rates can also be exported directly; for further detail see: [link](#).

IV. Labels used in our labelset

The labelset .csv file for use in coralnet is provided as a supplemental file.

Label ID	Short Code	Name	Functional Group
92	Algae	Algae	Algae
7770	BHCB	Bleached Hard Coral Branching	Hard coral
7773	BHCC	Bleached Hard Coral Columnar	Hard coral
7542	BHCE	Bleached Hard Coral Encrusting	Hard coral
7771	BHCF	Bleached Hard Coral Foliose	Hard coral
7772	BHCFL	Bleached Hard Coral Free-Living	Hard coral
7543	BHCM	Bleached Hard Coral Massive	Hard coral
101	CCA	CCA (crustose coralline algae)	Algae
105	D_coral	Dead coral	Hard Substrate
1398	DISCORAL	Diseased Coral	Hard coral
242	HC_branch	Hard Coral (branching)	Hard coral
3097	HC_column	Hard Coral (columnar)	Hard coral
239	HC_encr	Hard Coral (encrusting)	Hard coral
238	HC_fol	Hard Coral (foliose)	Hard coral
3095	HC_free	Hard Coral (free-living)	Hard coral
237	HC_massive	Hard Coral (massive)	Hard coral
3438	HS	Hard Substrate	Hard Substrate
982	Other Inv	Other invertebrate	Other Invertebrates
80	SC	Soft Coral	Other Invertebrates
95	Sediment	Soft coral_bleached	Other Invertebrates
5932	SOFT_BL	Sediment	Soft Substrate
1647	Unk	Unknown	Other

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